

35 **Keywords:** Geoinformatics; Historical constructions; Preventive conservation; Web-GIS;
36 Internet of Things; PlusCare system; HeritageCare platform; Geospatial database; Monitoring
37 network

38 **1 Introduction**

39
40 Preventive conservation can be considered as the most efficient approach for maintaining and
41 protecting heritage buildings and sites [1-3]. Unlike remedial approaches, this strategy is able to
42 save between 40% and 70% of the total maintenance costs by avoiding major interventions and
43 promoting systematic inspections and monitoring routines [2]. However, its effective
44 implementation entails different challenges [3], demanding the use of standardized and integrated
45 workflows for documentation, registration and management of the information along with proper
46 communication protocols between technicians (expert users) and buildings' owners/managers
47 (non-expert users) [4]. In the light of these considerations, and given the absence of a systematic
48 policy, the European project HeritageCare (Monitoring and preventive conservation of historic
49 and cultural heritage, ref. SOE1/P5/P0258) has been promoting the implementation of a
50 hierarchical digital-based preventive conservation system in South-West Europe. This system
51 draws inspiration from the Flemish Monumentenwacht [5,6] – a public organization which
52 influences daily maintenance practices in The Netherlands and Flanders – but introduces new
53 substantial developments in the form of digital tools to keep abreast of the times and enhance the
54 quality of the services provided [4]. The HeritageCare system relies on three complementary
55 levels of services, whose main pillar is a systematic inspection and monitoring process supported
56 by the latest advances in digitization and smart technologies (e.g. photogrammetry, drones, laser
57 scanning or Building Information Modelling, among others [7]). Service Level 1 (SL1 or
58 StandardCare) aims at providing a feasible, low-cost and rapid condition assessment of the
59 heritage buildings; Service Level 2 (SL2 or PlusCare) is devoted to integrating the information
60 collected during SL1 with an in-depth condition assessment of the building and its indoor assets,
61 including the monitoring of the most relevant physical and mechanical parameters; finally,
62 Service Level 3 (SL3 or TotalCare) integrates and manages all data gathered from SL1 and SL2

63 through the Building Information Modelling (BIM). Focus of the present paper is to present the
64 PlusCare protocol in detail, exploring the role played by the main social actors (inspectors on the
65 one hand and owners/managers of the heritage sites on the other hand) within the entire
66 conservation process.

67 The integration of information from different inspection and diagnosis techniques, core of the
68 PlusCare protocol, is reached through the geoinformatics [8]. This discipline, which includes data
69 acquisition methods such as photogrammetry, laser scanning or remote sensing, promotes the use
70 of geoinformation approaches, for preserving cultural heritage, like Geographical Information
71 Systems (GIS) or Building Information Models (BIM) [8]. The former are rooted in the
72 employment of a geospatial database that is able to store a great variety of alphanumeric
73 information as well as raster and vectorial products, all of them properly geolocalized [9]. Thanks
74 to this ability, there are plenty of applications that use GIS for heritage preservation at city [10,11]
75 and building levels [12-14] in which the information can be filtered according to different criteria.
76 The latter have emerged as an intelligent management system focused on the creation of full 3D
77 digital models populated with meaningful attributes related with the materials, construction
78 systems, damages, monitoring networks, and the like. This information integration is carried out
79 within an interoperable framework, which makes BIM approaches a very powerful tool for the
80 management of preventive conservation plans [15-17].

81 Complementary to GIS and BIM, several authors have proposed in the last few years the use of
82 virtual tours as potential tools for integrating information related with the valorisation and
83 conservation of heritage [18-20]. The main advantages of these tools are the intuitiveness of the
84 output - obtained by means of 360° spherical projections - and its low-cost, requiring only the use
85 of digital cameras equipped with fisheye lenses or even as-built 360° cameras [18-20]. This way,
86 the information contained within the heritage system is statically loaded through the software
87 used for generating the virtual tour. Among these applications, it is worth highlighting the work
88 carried out by Sánchez Aparicio et al. [18] which integrates 360° virtual tours populated by

89 different information sources with a geospatial database for the valorisation of the Mediaeval
90 Wall of Avila, also featuring filter options in order to make advanced GIS queries.

91 Taking into consideration these developments, the HeritageCare project aimed to make a step
92 forward towards the systematic implementation of a digital-based preventive conservation system
93 for the historical and cultural heritage in Southwestern Europe. To this end, a new WEB-GIS tool
94 was developed to exploit the potentialities offered by the geoinformatics through the combination
95 of the latest advances in virtualization, Internet of Things (IoT) - i.e. monitoring networks, and
96 interoperability protocols. All these technologies are blended into a unique web platform called
97 PlusCare system, integral part of the HeritageCare platform. The system is complemented by a
98 robust geospatial database that allows for advanced queries in order to improve the user
99 experience through immersive virtual tours across the heritage.

100 After describing the main goals of the PlusCare protocol in Section 2, together with the methods
101 and materials used to develop and implement it, Section 3 discusses the application of this tool to
102 the General Historical Library of the University of Salamanca, one of the most relevant heritage
103 structures within the Spanish territory. Thereafter, Section 4 describes the user experience using
104 the PlusCare system. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions emerged after testing
105 this new digital-based preventive conservation tool.

106 **2 The HeritageCare digital-based approach**

107 **2.1 The PlusCare protocol**

108 As highlighted in the introduction, the main goal of this work is to show in detail the development
109 phase of the PlusCare protocol, which corresponds to the second service level (SL2) of the
110 HeritageCare method. This level is conceived to increase the knowledge of the inspected heritage
111 buildings and related indoor assets, integrating and complementing the information collected in
112 SL1. The protocol includes two similar workflows depending on the existence or not of a previous
113 SL2 inspection (Figure 1).

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115 Figure 1: Workflows for the application of the PlusCare protocol according to the starting condition: a) absence of a
116 previous SL2 inspection; and b) existence of a previous SL2.

117 In either case, the application of the PlusCare protocol depends upon the execution of a prior SL1
118 inspection and it is a mandatory stage for the application of the subsequent inspection level (SL3).
119 The selection of the service level depends on the conservation needs of the building as well as on
120 the owner's requirements/financial availability. For a thorough description of the workflow and
121 tools required to implement the first and third levels of service (SL1 and SL3), the reader is
122 referred to Masciotta et al. [4].

123 2.2 The PlusCare system

124 The efficient implementation of the PlusCare protocol required the development of a tool able not
125 only to integrate different data sources (including the IoT), but also to provide an intuitive
126 environment from which buildings' owners and managers (non-expert users) could access all the
127 significant information for the effective preventive conservation of their heritage. To make this
128 possible, a novel Web-GIS system was created: PlusCare. Such a tool combines the latest
129 advances in geodatabase models, interoperability protocols and digitalization strategies, to enable
130 the proactive conservation of historical constructions. Figure 2 shows the flowchart of the system
131 as well as its main engines. As schematized, the PlusCare system converges into a dual web

132 environment: i) one for expert users; ii) another for non-expert users. Both environments will be
 133 detailed in the following sections.

134
 135 Figure 2: Flowchart of the PlusCare system and its main engines. The workflows carried out by the inspector are
 136 presented in grey and yellow.

137 **2.2.1 Expert-user environment**
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139 The main functionality of the expert-user environment is to store all the technical information
 140 collected prior, during and after HeritageCare inspections with the aim of better addressing the
 141 specific needs of the buildings and designing proper preventive conservation plans. This
 142 environment was developed with different web-based languages, such as PHP and JavaScript
 143 (programming language), HTML (markup language) and CSS (design language), among others.
 144 Due to the multiple and heterogeneous information progressively gathered through the application
 145 of the HeritageCare method, the platform was conceived to include several tabs according to the
 146 nature of each information source. With specific reference to the PlusCare system, after inserting
 147 a few general data about the inspection (e.g. date, duration, tools and methodologies, etc.), specific
 148 information is demanded (Figure 3): i) assets; ii) panorama photos; iii) monitoring data; iv) point

149 clouds; v) data records; vi) damages. The right body of the environment shows all the fields that
150 the expert user needs to fill in depending on the tab selected on the left sidebar.

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152 Figure 3: Expert user interface of the PlusCare System.

153 It is worth recalling that SL2 fields can only be filled upon completion of the SL1 inspection
154 report of the building under consideration, namely after the application of the StandardCare
155 protocol to that building. This ‘restriction’ is intrinsic to the HeritageCare method, as the system
156 consists of three sequential service levels, where each level includes the previous one and adds
157 new information for a more extended knowledge of the heritage ensemble. Further details in this
158 regard can be found in Ramos et al. [21] and Morais et al. [7].

159 2.2.1.1 Assets

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161 The proper execution of the PlusCare level involves an in-depth evaluation of the conservation
162 state of the assets found within the heritage building/site. Based on a common cataloguing
163 framework, assets are classified into four different groups: i) main integrated objects; ii)
164 exceptional integrated objects; iii) main movable objects; iv) exceptional movable objects. Each
165 of these groups includes a total of twelve categories, as exposed by Masciotta et al. [4].

166 For each group and each asset, the expert user is required to fill a four-section form specifying
167 the following information (Figure 4a):

- 168
- *Asset identification*: this first part includes all the general metadata related to the inspected object, such as the asset name or the asset category, among others. Its geospatial location within the 3D model as well as within the panoramic photos must be included via spatial coordinates (x,y,z for the point cloud and *pan, tilt* for the panoramas).

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 - *Environmental assessment*: this section comprises a few key information related to the environmental conditions at the moment of the asset inspection: i) main bioclimate indicators: luminosity, temperature and relative humidity; ii) environmental condition classification; iii) specific comments for the owner; and iv) possible consequences if the condition is not maintained. After assigning the grade, the condition classification is filled in an automatic way according to the rating system shown in Figure 5a.

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 - *Assessment of the conservation state*: this section includes the damage affecting the assets. To this end, the platform is linked to the HeritageCare Damage Atlas, which represents a fundamental supporting tool for the preliminary diagnosis of the observed pathologies during inspection activities as well as for the identification of appropriate mitigation actions (Figure 5b). For more details about the Damage Atlas, refer to Masciotta et al. [4]. For each identified damage, the technician has to report information related to its severity and risk, as well as a short description of the damage with complementary images and further comments on possible consequences, if no action is undertaken, or recommendations to prevent the damage progression.

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 - *Damage summary*: this part of the form is automatically filled according to the information reported in the aforementioned fields. A summary of the asset inspection is shown, including the condition classification, the damage extent, the risk and urgency of remedial measures. The final condition classification of the asset is computed as the round weighted sum of the singles grades assigned to each detected damage.

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Figure 4: Graphical appearance of the expert-user environment: a) when the technician fills a “movable asset” form; b) when the technician uploads the panoramic images used for generating the virtual tour of the building/site.

a)

Class No.	Condition Classification	Symptoms	Urgency Risk Classification	Comments
0	Good	No symptoms	Long term	No immediate actions required Preventive monitoring is necessary
1	Fair	Minor Symptoms	Medium term	The condition of the fabric is not perfect but does not need immediate action Monitoring is necessary to prevent further decay
2	Poor	Moderately Strong Symptoms	Short term	The condition of the fabric is such that it needs timely repair or additional inspection and diagnosis work
3	Bad	Major Symptoms	Urgent and Immediate	Urgent repair is necessary Urgent additional inspection and diagnosis work
NA/NI	Not Accessible	Parts not (safely) accessible	Not Inspected	Parts that are 'not inspected' are either not (safely) accessible for the building inspectors or not visible

Figure 5: Inspection protocol for assets: a) condition classification (environment and conservation assessment); b) excerpt from the damage Atlas used to support the inspection stage of the assets.

2.2.1.2 Panorama photos

The form entitled *Panorama photos* is devoted to the storage of 360° images for the generation of the virtual tour of the heritage building/site (Figure 4b). The technician only needs to upload the panoramic photos in one of the most common formats, such as *.JPG*, *.PNG* or *.TIFF*, together with the location in which each panoramic image was taken, and a short description of the protocol used for data acquisition and data processing.

The virtual tour is generated in the external low-cost solution Pano2VR®. In order to adapt this software to the requirements of the platform, the in-house plugin *HeritageCare4Pano2VR* was created (Figure 6a). Some extra features were added for preventive conservation purposes, namely a menu integrating a direct link to the SL1 inspection report as well as to the 3D point cloud of the building/site, and the possibility of creating hotspots of damages, assets, monitoring

211 points and data records linked to the corresponding information stored in the HeritageCare
212 database.

213 It is worth mentioning that each time the technician uploads new information to the platform and
214 fills the fields corresponding with its spatial location, the platform creates a new hotspot inside
215 the virtual tour which is directly linked to a HTML page containing all the relevant information
216 concerning that specific hotspot. The damages detected during SL1 inspection can be also
217 georeferenced by adding their coordinates to the corresponding label (Figure 6b).

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Figure 6: Visual appearance of a) *Pano2VR* and b) *Damages* tabs.

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224 **2.2.1.3** *Monitoring data*
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226 Monitoring tasks can be considered an essential part of a proper preventive conservation plan.
227 Hence, the PlusCare system includes a specific tab to store and manage all the information
228 associated to the monitoring sensor network installed in the inspected heritage building. In this
229 regard, the technician needs to specify (Figure 7a): i) the identification number of the nodes
230 composing the network; ii) the monitored parameters measured by each node; iii) the date of
231 installation; iv) the main technical characteristics of the sensor; v) the type of connection; vi) the
232 weight and dimensions of the nodes; vii) the maintenance requirements. Regarding the second
233 label, i.e. the monitored quantities, the current version of the PlusCare system offers a total of 27
234 different parameters, including bioclimate (e.g. temperature, CO₂, luminosity or relative
235 humidity), structural (e.g. inclination, crack width or maximum acceleration) and biological (e.g.
236 presence of xylophagous) parameters.

237 To obtain the information associated with the periodic or continuous measurements recorded by
238 the sensors, the PlusCare system implements a *JavaScript Object Notation* (JSON)
239 communication protocol between the platform itself and the server that stores the monitoring data
240 [22]. In this file, the information demanded by the platform concerns the node identification
241 number, the measured parameters, the values captured by the different sensors placed within the
242 same node, and the sensor status. This latter is used to apply a specific colour grade to each
243 monitored parameter in the non-expert user environment. To this end, the PlusCare protocol
244 resorts to the use of key-performance indicators (KPIs) in order to define different threshold
245 ranges for which the structural behaviour of the building or its environmental conditions can be
246 considered good, acceptable or non-acceptable [23-25]. These KPIs are defined within the
247 monitoring server, which sends this information in the form of integer values to the PlusCare
248 system. These values range from 0 to 2 according to the detected degree of risk/acceptability: 0
249 for a good status; 1 if a potential risk exists; and 2 if the risk is high.

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Figure 7: Interface of the PlusCare system: a) *Monitoring Network* tab; b) *Point Cloud* tab.

253 2.2.1.4 Point clouds

254 This form is conceived for the inspector to upload the whole 3D point cloud of the heritage
255 building/site. The PlusCare protocol allows the use of different recording strategies depending on
256 the complexity and size of the cultural heritage site that needs to be digitalized [4].

257 The current version of the PlusCare system implements the Potree library [26], since it allows to
258 render large point clouds through the use of an Octree visualization system. Additionally, this
259 viewer includes instruments for both expert and non-expert users, such as measurement tools,
260 clipping tools to visualize different parts of the model, and navigation tools. Besides, Potree
261 viewer is able to integrate, by means of the so-called annotations, graphical and text information
262 within the point cloud [26]. This feature is used by the system to plot relevant information on the
263 3D point cloud, thus creating a dynamic 3D model.

264 According to what exposed hitherto, the inspector needs to upload the point cloud and then the
265 platform automatically computes the Octree structure. For documentation and management
266 purposes, the technician is also required to insert information about the name of the place
267 digitalized, its location, the date of collection as well as a short description about the capturing
268 and processing of data (Figure 7b).

269 **2.2.1.5** *Data records*

270 This tab is dedicated to the uploading and storage of all supplementary data and information that
271 can contribute to improve the knowledge about the heritage building/site (e.g. in situ
272 investigations, like sonic or borescope tests, dynamic identification tests, etc.), as well as its
273 history and conservation state (Figure 8). To this end, the technician needs to fill in and upload a
274 standardized *PDF* form summarizing this additional data records and highlighting the principal
275 results obtained. To complete the form, the type of data record and its spatial coordinates both in
276 the point cloud and in the panoramic photos must be specified.

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Figure 8: Appearance of the *Data Record* tab.

279 **2.2.2** *Non-expert user environment*

280 As highlighted in the introduction, the success of any preventive conservation plan passes through
281 the proper and fluid communication between the technician(s) and the owner or manager of the
282 heritage building/site. In order to facilitate this transfer of information, the PlusCare system
283 includes a non-expert user environment that allows to consult all essential data reflecting the

284 conservation state of the inspected historical artefact in a friendly way. The intuitiveness of this
285 environment originates from the use of 360° photos and a 3-colour grading scale that
286 automatically rates the acceptability and degree of risk of the monitored values. This imagery
287 input is enclosed into an improved virtual tour with a geospatial database that enables to access
288 the information related to the inspections carried out by the technicians. Accordingly, the interface
289 integrates two main sections (Figure 9): i) a left sidebar showing all the information accessible
290 from the database; ii) a right section including the virtual tour composed by 360° panoramic
291 images in spherical projection with pre-defined hotspots associated with the assets, monitoring
292 nodes, data records and damages created by the inspector in the expert-user environment. This
293 graphical user interface is complemented by a bottom navigation bar that allows to consult the
294 3D point cloud of the site and the SL1 condition report (Figure 10a). As shown in Figure 9, this
295 navigation bar includes nine different groups of buttons (from left to right): i) button *a* to
296 show/hide the map; ii) button *b* to enable/disable the gyroscope app; iii) button *c* to visualize the
297 environment in full-screen mode; iv) button *d* to see or hide the hotspots of the virtual tour; v)
298 group of buttons *e* to move the panoramas up, down, left and right; vi) button *f* to load the SL1
299 condition report; vii) button *g* to connect the virtual tour with the 3D point cloud viewer; viii)
300 button *h* to define the language; and ix) button *i* to hide/unhide the sidebar menu. It is worth
301 mentioning that the platform includes a specific library for reading the data coming from the
302 inertial units of mobile devices (tablets/smartphones). The use of this library makes possible to
303 generate an augmented reality system since it lets synchronize the real point of view of the user
304 with the virtual point of view of the platform.

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Figure 9: Interface of the non-expert user environment with the tab *Additional Tests* unfolded in the left sidebar. The buttons placed inside the red rectangle correspond to the group of buttons *e*.

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Figure 10: Reports automatically generated from the platform based on the inspection outcome: a) SL1 report about the building condition; b) SL2 report about the asset condition.

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314 The left sidebar of the graphical user interface is structured in a hierarchical way with the aim of
315 grouping data properly. This structure consists of four levels:

- 316 • *Assets*: this tab includes the four main groups defined in Section 2.2.1.1.
- 317 • *Damages*: this tab comprises the possible damages that can be found during the inspection
318 organized into four macro-categories: i) building envelope; ii) building interior; iii)
319 technical installations and equipment; iv) accessibility and hygiene.
- 320 • *Advanced monitoring*: this tab lists all the nodes belonging to the monitoring system
321 installed in the heritage building/site.
- 322 • *Additional tests*: this tab is used to link information about further tests carried out onsite
323 and incorporates 6 sub-levels: i) 2D drawings; ii) test results; iii) reports; iv) photos; v)
324 detailed historical survey; vi) other documents.

325 Whenever the platform is accessed, the PlusCare system makes a request to the database to load
326 all the information collected by the inspector(s) for the preventive conservation plan of the
327 building, showing the number of items available in each tab of the left sidebar (Figure 9).
328 Complementarily, the platform stores in hidden fields the associated spatial data, namely: i)
329 number of panoramas; ii) *pan* and *tilt* angles. These data permit, by means of a JavaScript order,
330 to place the point of view of the virtual tour directly in the area to which the information belongs
331 (e.g. if users click on node 1, the platform places the point of view of the virtual tour in the area
332 where node 1 is located). This information is showed in a 360° environment through the so-called
333 hotspots. Each hotspot includes information about a particular asset, damage, test record or
334 monitoring node, generally in the form of a simple and easy-to-read report (Figure 10b and Table
335 1). Additionally, each hotspot has a direct link to the 3D point cloud viewer where pertinent data
336 about the consulted item are shown.

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Table 1: Hotspot system used by the PlusCare system (non-expert user environment).

Data category	Icon	Data associated	Information shown in the point cloud
Damage		Damage Atlas form about the specific damage observed.	Class, sub-class and sub-sub-class of damage, features description, condition classification, symptoms, risk and urgency of intervention.
Asset		Inspection report of the asset(s).	Name of the asset, detected damages and damage summary (condition classification, symptoms, risk and urgency of intervention).
Advanced monitoring		Real-time updates of the values of the monitored parameters, each one with the relevant symbol coloured in accordance with the established threshold levels.	Symbols and values of the monitored parameters. These symbols have a specific colour grade according to the KPI implemented and the relative threshold values.
Additional tests		Report(s) with data and meaningful information from other tests	Name of the record, date of collection, description, data interpretation.

342 **2.2.2.1** *Advanced search*

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344 Given the considerable amount of information stored, the PlusCare system includes an advanced

345 search tool to ease the seeking process. This functionality allows to filter all the data according to

346 different criteria, namely:

347 • *Assets*: the assets inspected in the building can be filtered based on their category, overall

348 condition, recommended inspection periodicity and location across the building.

349 • *Damages*: damages can be filtered by overall condition, inspection periodicity, class of

350 damage and location across the building.

351 • *Advanced monitoring*: all the sensors connected to the installed monitoring network can

352 be filtered by type of sensor, node status as well as by their spatial location.

353 • *Additional tests*: further tests and information stored within the HeritageCare platform

354 can be filtered according to the test/record location across the building.

355 It is worth mentioning that several filtering criteria can be used within the same search, e.g. users
356 can filter all the sensors placed in the first floor that are able to measure the relative humidity
357 (Figure 11).

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Figure 11: Example of advanced data filtering in the PlusCare platform.

360 **3 Application to the General Historical Library of the University of Salamanca**

361 **3.1 The PlusCare protocol**

362 During the project, the HeritageCare method and its related tools were successfully tested across
363 a considerable number of heritage buildings in Southwestern Europe. Particularly, the PlusCare
364 system was first validated in Spain with the General Historical Library of the University of
365 Salamanca. This building belongs to the well-known *Escuelas Mayores*, declared a Place of
366 Cultural Interest in 1931 (Figure 12a). It is located in the historical centre of Salamanca and dates
367 from the 15th century. The construction suffered several alterations along the history. Nowadays,
368 its main façade is considered the best piece of Spanish artworks executed in Plateresque style
369 (Figure 12b), being the symbol of the third oldest university still in operation in the world, as well
370 as the oldest university in Spain. The General Historical Library stands behind this remarkable
371 façade. It features a squared plan with a length of 41 m and a width of about 11.5 m (Figure 13).
372 Its current appearance dates back to 1749 as a result of the restoration works carried out by Manuel
373 de Lara Churriguera (Figure 14). The inner space of the library is covered with a vaulted system

374 characterized by ten lunettes, four half pointed arches and polygonal vaults at the extremes, hiding
375 the ceramic tiled roof above supported by timber trusses.

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a)

b)

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Figure 12: *Escuelas Mayores*: a) location; and b) general view of its main façade.

a)

b)

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Figure 13: 2D drawings of the General Historical Library of the University of Salamanca: a) plan; and b) longitudinal section A-A'.

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Figure 14: Interior view of the General Historical Library.

384 Today the library is used as a museum and repository, holding 2,774 manuscripts, 483 incunabula
385 and about 62,000 printed volumes from the 16th, 17th and 18th centuries arranged on wooded

386 shelves carved in Baroque style. Additionally, the Historical Library holds ten terrestrial, celestial
387 and armillary spheres made of wood, paper and metal, as well as several vitrines, tables and chairs
388 in leather and wood [27] (Figure 14).

389 This astonishing diversity and peculiarity of assets requires the elaboration of a robust preventive
390 conservation plan to avoid any possible degradation phenomenon deriving from the inappropriate
391 maintenance of the infrastructure or even from events that can promote aggressive bioclimate
392 conditions.

393 3.2 Data collection and documentation

394 The Library was first inspected by an equipped team of HeritageCare professionals who applied
395 the StandardCare protocol foreseen for SL1. This protocol allows a rapid condition screening of
396 the conservation status and uses a 4-colour grading scale to associate a degree of severity to each
397 observed damage [4]. This *modus operandi* permits to rank the overall building condition based
398 on the average grade scored by each inspected building item, thus assisting in the definition of
399 priorities of intervention or, alternatively, additional inspection and diagnosis works (Figure 10a
400 and Figure 15) [4].

401

402 Figure 15: Chart of the building interior highlighting the priority of intervention together with the possible
403 consequences if no preventive measure is adopted.

404 With respect to the case study analysed, one full working day was necessary to perform the on-
405 site inspection of the Library. To guarantee a real-time digitization of the inspection process and
406 speed up reporting times, the inspection team resorted to a tablet equipped with a specific
407 application developed within the HeritageCare project. Based on the SL1 outcome, the state of
408 conservation of the Library was deemed acceptable. However, a detailed technical inspection of
409 the roof covering as well as the control of bioclimate parameters were recommended to prevent
410 possible degradation processes. As a result, a higher inspection level was implemented by
411 applying the PlusCare protocol, thus involving the stages detailed in Section 2.1.

412 **3.3 Site digitalization**

413 To obtain high-resolution information about the geometry and onsite conditions of the Library, a
414 digitalization campaign was carried out to collect panoramic images and capture 3D point clouds.
415 The former were acquired by means of the Canon 700D® DLRS camera. This DLRS camera has
416 a 22.3 x 14.9 mm CMOS sensor with 18 MPx resolution (5196 x 3463 px), a pixel size of 4.29
417 µm and a crop factor of 1.61. This device was equipped with a Sigma 8 mm circular fisheye lens
418 with a maximum aperture of f/3.5 and a focus engine. Each station required a total of seven shots
419 with 60% of overlap between them. As for the present campaign, 13 equirectangular panoramas
420 were taken (Figure 16): i) 1 to digitalize the main façade; ii) 4 to capture the outdoor space of the
421 inner cloister; iii) 2 for representing the hall of the inner cloister next to the Library; iv) 6 for the
422 digitalization of the Library. The different shots were stitched with the open-source software
423 Hugin®. It is noted that each panorama was captured in the same position as the laser scanner
424 station aiming at colouring the TLS point clouds. This was possible thanks to the use of the
425 platform designed by Del Pozo et al. [28] (Figure 16b). Afterwards, the “basic” virtual tour was
426 created in Pano2VR® with the assistance of the plugin *HeritageCare4Pano2VR*.

a)

b)

427

428 Figure 16: Result of the digitalization stage: a) plan view with the location of the stations; b) optimized point cloud
429 within the open-source software CloudCompare®. Note: blue dots represent scan stations with panoramic images and
430 red dots indicate stations with panoramic images only.

431 The 3D digitalization of the Historical Library was performed by means of the light-weight TLS
432 Faro Focus 120®. This laser scanner is based on the phase shift physical principle with a
433 measurement range from 0.6 to 120 m, a capture rate from 122,000 to 976,00 points per second
434 and a nominal accuracy of 2 mm at 25 m in normal conditions of illumination and reflectivity. As
435 a result, 6 scan stations were needed to record the Historical Library. All these scan stations were
436 registered in a common coordinate system using to this end the Iterative Closest Points algorithm
437 [29] by applying the strategy defined by Sánchez Aparicio et al. [30]. The final error after the
438 alignment of the different point clouds was 3 ± 2 mm. The huge amount of captured data, with a

439 total of 140,070,904 points, required an optimization stage that comprised the use of a spatial
440 decimation filter with a threshold of 0.005 m. This allowed to obtain a reduced 3D representation
441 of the Historical Library consisting of 18,209,138 points, namely 13% as compared to the original
442 point cloud (Figure 16). Finally, this point cloud was uploaded to the PlusCare system in .LAZ
443 format in order to be converted by the Potree script for visualization purposes (Figure 16b). The
444 time spent for the complete digitalization process, including data capturing and processing,
445 required two working days by a group of 2 inspectors.

446 **3.4 Tracking the bioclimate parameters**

447 Most of assets located within the General Historical Library of the University of Salamanca are
448 made of organic materials such as wood, leather and paper. Thus, the control of bioclimate
449 parameters is of utmost importance to ensure the proper conservation of such a valuable legacy.
450 According to Pavlogeorgatos [31], the four main environmental parameters that can promote the
451 deterioration of assets located in libraries and museums are:

- 452 • *Relative humidity*: out-of-tolerance values of this parameter can cause changes in size,
453 shape as well as biological and chemical reactions of the exhibits.
- 454 • *Temperature*: variations of indoor temperature can lead to a variety of reactions such as
455 the acceleration of chemical processes (e.g. corrosion rate of cellulose), the movement of
456 moisture or even material expansion.
- 457 • *Luminosity*: natural and artificial illumination sources can induce oxidation of the
458 components, thereby promoting the deterioration and corruption of several materials.
- 459 • *Atmospheric pollution*: gasses, such as sulphur and nitrogen oxides, ozone and other
460 atmospheric particles, can promote chemical attacks.

461 **3.4.1 Monitoring network**

462 To better address the conservation needs of the Library, an advanced monitoring network was
463 installed in the hall to keep the main bioclimate indicators under control. The selected measuring
464 equipment was the MHS (Monitoring Heritage System) [32], a monitoring system purposely

465 developed for cultural heritage buildings by the Santa Maria La Real Foundation. Type, number
466 and location of the sensors were decided based on the outcomes of the SL1 inspection and pre-
467 monitoring stage, paying attention to minimizing their visual impact inside the Library. The
468 system is active since July 2019 and consists of:

- 469 • 15 relative humidity and temperature sensors (*HT*), of which 10 ambient and 5 surface
470 sensors, plus 8 combined sensors measuring relative humidity, surface temperature and
471 brightness (*HT+B*).
- 472 • 2 xylophagous sensors (*X*) to detect the presence of this type of insects into the wooden
473 shelves;
- 474 • 1 solar radiation sensor (*SR*) to measure the radiant energy received by the sun and
475 emitted into the surrounding environment;
- 476 • 1 carbon dioxide sensor (*CO₂*) to check average concentrations of this trace gas inside the
477 Library;
- 478 • 1 presence detector sensor (*PD*) to track people presence and eventually switch off
479 unnecessary lighting, air conditioning, etc.;
- 480 • 1 meteo station (*MS*) to record outer air temperature, humidity, barometric pressure, wind
481 direction and velocity, precipitations, rain duration, hail as well as solar radiation and
482 carbon dioxide.

483 It is noted that ambient temperature and humidity sensors were placed at different heights in order
484 to catch possible changes in elevation of the monitored parameters. Complementary to the
485 installation, the technician is required to insert in the PlusCare system the metadata associated
486 with the monitoring nodes.

Node status	Date status	Temperature	Temperature status
1		23.455	G

Relative humidity	Relative humidity status	Presence	Presence status

Figure 17: Monitoring network form with the data associated to each node.

487
488

489 The local nodes of the monitoring system collect the relevant values from the sensors and transmit
490 this data to a central node (CN) by means of a Zigbee communication protocol. The PlusCare
491 system makes a *JSON* query to the monitoring database each 30 minutes in order to update the
492 values of the tracked parameters.

493 3.4.2 Range of tolerances for preventive conservation

494 As mentioned in Section 2.2.1.3, and with the aim of guiding the non-expert user in the preventive
495 conservation of the building, the PlusCare system integrates the concept of *Sensor Status*.
496 Basically, three colour grades are used to automatically rate the different variables captured by
497 the monitoring network, being possible to check in real-time whether each parameter falls outside
498 the established tolerance range and could promote material degradation. To define this range, the
499 implementation of proper Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is required. For the present case
500 study, the KPI definition by Corgnati et al. [25] is adopted. Generally, a KPI identifies the
501 percentage of measurements in which the monitored parameter lies within a required range. This
502 way, if the 90% or more of the measurements lies within the pre-established range, the *Sensor*
503 *Status* throws a value of 0; if this percentage ranges between 85% and 90% the *Sensor Status*
504 throws a value of 1; otherwise, for a percentage under 85%, the *Sensor Status* is set as 2. This
505 concept is extended to all the monitoring network with the exception of the xylophagous detectors,
506 for which only two *Sensor Status* are defined: i) 0, if the sensor does not detect any xylophagous

507 activity, and ii) 2, if the sensor detects the presence of xylophagous activity within the wood.
508 According to what stated above, a KPI can be expressed as follows:

$$KPI = \frac{N_{in}}{N_{tot}} \quad (1)$$

509 where N_{in} represents the number of measurements within the defined tolerances and N_{tot} is the
510 total number of measurements.
511

512 The calculation of the KPIs requires the definition of a set of case-specific tolerance ranges for
513 the different monitored variables, including indoor climate parameters. In this regard, various
514 standards can be considered [33]. As for this work, the tolerances defined by the guideline PAS
515 198:2012 were taken into account [34]. Table 2 shows the set of tolerances implemented for the
516 Historical Library.

517 Table 2: Tolerances considered for the indoor climate evaluation.

Parameter	Recommended range
Temperature	14-28 °C
Relative Humidity	40-60%
Luminosity	maximum of 50 lux

518 3.5 Assets condition survey

519 Complementary to the monitoring activities, the PlusCare protocol entails the inspection of the
520 integrated and movable assets located within the heritage building. Due to the huge amount of
521 assets treasured in the Library, only the most representative ones of each area were inspected: i)
522 the two vitrines (main movable objects); ii) one Earth Globe (main movable object); iii) 21 books
523 (exceptional movable objects).

524 First, a visual inspection was carried out with the aid of the HeritageCare damage atlas in order
525 to identify possible deterioration processes, but no remarkable damage was observed. Regarding
526 the environmental assessment, several in-situ measures were taken for the most relevant
527 bioclimate parameters: humidity, temperature and luminosity. The captured values were
528 considered acceptable at the time of the inspection. However, the monitoring data allowed to track
529 some period of the year in which the luminosity values exceeded the recommended ones.
530 Accordingly, it was decided to keep the UV levels of this area under control in order to prevent

531 values that could promote the photodegradation of the assets in the long term. This consideration
532 was included in the relevant section of the asset inspection form of the PlusCare system, grading
533 the environmental assessment as poor and recommending the use of UV filters on the library glass
534 windows. The same conclusions were obtained during the assessment of the Earth Globe.

535 In parallel, a total of 21 books from eight different knowledge areas were inspected. Some
536 common damage was detected in all books, particularly discoloration and material loss. The
537 environmental condition was classified as poor due to the possibility of having photodegradation
538 processes induced by the UV radiation, as highlighted during the inspection of the vitrines.

539 Apart from the conservation and environmental assessment, the inspection form of each asset was
540 filled with metadata information, as well as with their spatial position within the 3D model and
541 the corresponding panoramic image. Filling this information is compulsory for the PlusCare
542 system to create automatically the asset hotspots within the virtual tour of the heritage building.

543 **3.6 Test records**

544 To finalize the PlusCare inspection of the Library, a re-compilation of the main results obtained
545 during the experimental campaign was included in the tab *Test records*. In particular, the
546 information from both the digitalization campaign and the geometrical survey of the library was
547 uploaded to the platform using the standardized *PDF* template available for download (Figure
548 18).

549

550

Figure 18: Appearance of the standardized PDF file with the description of the test results.

551

552 4 Non-expert user experience

553

The PlusCare system also features an intuitive environment for non-expert users. The potential of this environment can be measured by the ease in which the multiple and heterogeneous information generated by the expert user is transferred to the non-expert user during the virtual tour, which represents the main output of the PlusCare protocol.

557

All essential information for the primary conservation needs and ordinary maintenance of the building is condensed into a simple and clear report which can be easily accessed by the end-user while navigating through the virtual tour just by clicking on the heart icon (button *f*) of the bottom navigation bar of the graphical interface (Figure 9a). Across the document, the information appears in different colours. Building items in good conservation state are highlighted in green, implying that no immediate preventive action is required; those in fair or poor conditions are highlighted in yellow and orange, respectively, where the former colour suggests medium-term

563

564 preventive actions and the latter short-term measures; finally, building items in bad condition are
565 reported in red, meaning that urgent repair actions are necessary to prevent further decay (Figure
566 19a). Thanks to this graphical system the owner/manager can perceive at a glance which priority
567 of intervention should be considered if some building items do not appear in good condition. This
568 eye-catching content is then complemented with useful information about the possible
569 consequences for the building.

570 The 3D icon of the bottom navigation bar of the PlusCare interface gives the user the possibility
571 to access and browse through the tridimensional high-resolution survey of the heritage site. The
572 visualization is boosted by the Octree system, allowing to check it on mobile devices (Figure
573 19b).

574

575 Figure 19: Non-expert user environment: a) consultation of SL2 condition report (yellow paragraphs indicate a fair
576 damage condition, while green means that the damage severity is low); b) consultation of measurements within the
577 3D point cloud.

578 **4.1 Information available through hotspots**

579 The rest of the information stored by the inspectors into the PlusCare database, such as the assets
580 condition, the damages or any additional record (see Section 2.2.1.5), is plotted in the non-expert
581 user environment by means of pre-defined hotspots inserted within the pertinent 360° photos that
582 compose the virtual tours. The full list of hotspots among which the user can navigate is available
583 in the left sidebar, grouped by category (Figure 20a and b). The optimal connection between the
584 database and the virtual tour ensures a quick browsing among the different objects directly from
585 the sidebar menu of the interface, and regardless of the filter applied for the advanced search. In
586 this way, if the user does look for a specific asset and selects its name, the platform automatically
587 places the user's point of view in the area where the selected asset is located (Figure 20b).
588 Furthermore, if the user clicks on that object hotspot, a window pops up allowing to consult both
589 the asset inspection report (Figure 20b) and its location within the 3D model (Figure 20c). The
590 transfer of information associated with damage and test record hotspots is plotted in the same
591 way.

a)

b)

c)

592

593

594

595

Figure 20: Non-expert user environment: a) consulting information about the asset condition; b) pop-up box related to the asset hotspot (yellow paragraphs indicate that the environmental conditions are not appropriate for the selected asset); c) 3D model

596 Apart from the aforementioned features, the non-expert user environment includes the possibility
597 of capturing the values of the device gyroscopes. Basically, the point of view of the platform can
598 rotate according to the angular variation captured by the gyroscopes. Such a feature places the
599 PlusCare system of the HeritageCare platform as a potential alternative to standard augmented
600 reality systems (Figure 21).

601

602

603

604

Figure 21: Response of the platform when the gyroscope feature is active: a) consulting a damage hotspot;
b) checking a sensor hotspot.

605 4.2 Visualization of the monitoring data

606 Like damages, assets and test records, also monitoring data can be consulted directly by the non-
607 expert user just by clicking on the corresponding hotspots. Each of these hotspots gives access to
608 real-time updates of the parameters measured by the sensors along with their location within the
609 3D point cloud. The environment uses the *Sensor Status* variable described in Section 3.4 to plot
610 colour-based warnings of the monitored quantities through a pop-up window: i) green icon, when
611 the variable has a value of 0, thus the monitored parameter is within the acceptable tolerance
612 range; ii) yellow icon, if it has a value of 1, meaning that the monitored parameter is not always
613 within the defined thresholds; and iii) red icon, if the sensor status is 2, which indicates that the
614 value of the considered parameter deviates from the acceptable limits. By means of this visual
615 grading scale the user can get a quick idea about the microclimate conditions existing within his
616 building (Figure 22a). Moreover, thanks to the advanced search options featured by the PlusCare
617 system, the user can easily filter the nodes of the monitoring network and get to know immediately
618 which sensors are providing values out of the recommended tolerances. The way to consult this
619 information is substantially improved when using the gyroscope values of the smartphone or
620 tablet (Figure 21b). Information about the monitoring data is also shown on the 3D point cloud of
621 the building (Figure 22b).

622

623 Figure 22: Colour-based warnings applied to the sensor network: a) real-time updates of the monitored parameters for
624 node 30; b) 3D model with superimposed information about the selected node.

625 5 Conclusions

626 A new paradigm for the preventive conservation of historical sites was presented in this paper.
627 Considering the leading role that digitization is assuming in the context of heritage conservation,
628 this work aimed to show the progressive development of one the major digital outputs of the
629 HeritageCare methodology, i.e. the PlusCare system. The transfer of information to the non-
630 expert users is smooth and user-friendly, offering owners and managers of heritage sites an
631 interactive and intuitive tool that facilitates monitoring activities and supports decision making
632 on preventive conservation actions. Full details about the PlusCare system are provided in the
633 paper and its validation is performed through a case-study application having as object of

634 investigation one of the most representative Spanish cultural heritage buildings: the Historical
635 Library of the University of Salamanca. From the validation of this digital-based tool, it is possible
636 to draw the following conclusions:

- 637 • The PlusCare system is a Web-GIS application of the HeritageCare platform rooted in
638 the latest advances in digitalization technologies, monitoring networks and IoT concepts
639 that is paving the way for a new paradigm in preventive conservation.
- 640 • The integration of a geospatial database makes possible to streamline the management of
641 large blocks of multidisciplinary information, allowing to filter the great amount of stored
642 data according to different criteria.
- 643 • The use of colour grading scales to rate the conservation state of the assets located within
644 the heritage site allows a better interpretation of the inspection outcome by the non-expert
645 users and can assist them in prioritizing preventive conservation actions.
- 646 • The implementation of KPIs and colour-based warning levels associated with the
647 monitoring data also provides a straightforward metric for the end-users to understand
648 the acceptability of the recorded values and adopt condition-based maintenance
649 measures.
- 650 • The exploitation of pyramidal loading schemes for both the 3D point clouds and the 360°
651 images enables to optimize the computational requirements. Additionally, according to
652 the tests carried out to evaluate the time response of the platform, when using an ordinary
653 PC, the average response time of the platform is just 1.8 seconds for loading the main
654 interface; 0.5 seconds for loading the results of the advanced search; and 4.1 seconds for
655 loading the whole 3D point cloud (lower Octree level). Instead, if the platform is loaded
656 in a standard smartphone, the average response time is 4.0 seconds for the main interface;
657 0.5 seconds for loading the results of the advanced search and an instantaneous response
658 of the gyroscopes when this feature is activated; 8.2 seconds for rendering the whole 3D
659 point cloud with the lower Octree level. These results can be considered more than
660 acceptable to guarantee a good user experience.

661 • The intuitiveness of the panoramic photos combined with geospatial information and
662 mobile devices further enhance the users' experience while navigating across the
663 heritage. This experience can be a great supporting tool to engage the main social actors
664 in the proactive preventive conservation of their legacy.

665 • Unlike BIM approaches, the PlusCare system does not require any structured data
666 template nor specific object libraries for the 3D virtual reconstruction of the heritage.
667 Metric and morphologic values are equally important, and they can be profitably
668 exploited to cross-check and describe accurately the quantitative information that an
669 HBIM-based model should contain. Moreover, the final output of the PlusCare system is
670 much more user-friendly and accessible by non-expert users. Indeed, PlusCare has been
671 conceived as a preparatory level to TotalCare, the last of the three service levels of the
672 HeritageCare methodology, whose focus is the integration and management of all
673 information collected from previous service levels through an intelligent digital model
674 built in BIM environment.

675 Future works will be focused on integrating new features into the system. On the one hand, it is
676 planned to improve the uploading process of the expert user environment. This will enable to add
677 new information (e.g. assets, damages, monitoring nodes) directly onsite with a mobile device,
678 thereby reducing the back-office work. On the other hand, efforts will be made to achieve a
679 complete integration between the new digitalization approaches, e.g. back-pack mobile mapping
680 systems, and the as-built 360° cameras in order to speed up the data acquisition.

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